
ENTREPRENEURIAL APPRENTICESHIP AND PERSONAL ECONOMIC DEVELOPMENT AMONG IGBO PEOPLE (Incubating and Multiplying Business Moguls)

By

Nwabuatu, Emmanuel Nnajiubah
Department of Entrepreneurship,
Ignatius Ajuru University of Education,
Rumuolumeni, Rivers state.
Email: emmanuel.nwabuatu@iaue.edu.ng

Abstract

The title of this study is entrepreneurial apprenticeship and personal economic development among Igbo people in eastern Nigeria. The study examined the relationship between entrepreneurial apprenticeship and personal economic development among the Igbo ethnic nationality in Eastern Nigeria. The study identified and examined three approaches to entrepreneurial apprenticeship practiced by Igbo people namely: commercial apprenticeship (Imu-Ahia), Craft-man apprenticeship (Imu-Oruaka) and Agent apprenticeship (Igba osoafia). The three approaches to entrepreneurial apprenticeship generally and commonly known in Igbo land as Igba-boyi or Igba odibo mean apprenticeship. Structured Questionnaires were used as instrument for data collection. The study employed correlational research design. The population of study was 150 dealers in food stuff. The study adopted convenience sampling method and relied on use of primary data generated through questionnaire. Hypotheses were tested using Spearman rank correlation coefficient. Hypotheses were tested at 5% degree of freedom and the acceptance and rejection of the null hypotheses was that $P < 0.05$. The result of the tested hypotheses for the three dimensions of entrepreneurial apprenticeship with rho vales of 0.788, 0.856 and 0.899 all positively correlated to personal economic development. The study concluded that entrepreneurial apprenticeship in Igbo land is on the job practical training leading to development of competences in commerce, craft and agency. That the competence development through entrepreneurial apprenticeship exercise is equivalent to seven years of studying in the university. That the three approaches to entrepreneurial apprenticeship among the Igbo people, visa-vice Imu-Ahia, Imu –Oruaka and Igba-oso-afia provides easy and legitimate time honoured route to endowment with capital for individual /personal startup / investment and continued access to mentorship. The study recommended that entrepreneurial apprenticeship should be integrated into the career study for the students beginning from primary to university.

Keywords: Entrepreneurship, Apprenticeship, Imu-Ahia, Imu-Oruaka and Igba-oso-afia.

INTRODUCTION

Before the modern era of mechanized agriculture, various types of farming like plantation, and animal husbandry are the primary source of income for the majority of the people living in rural communities in Africa. But from time immemorial, Igbo people of the Eastern Nigeria have always been known for their instinctual drives and astute in commerce, craft and agency. They are achievement oriented people. They are very tenacious and aggressive in pursuit of any purpose of their choice.

They have propensity towards micro, small and medium-sized indigenous manufacturing and commercial outfit. They have propensity to establish and engage in local technical, fabrication and engineering industries known as black Smith (such technical, fabrication and engineering business activities is known in Igbo land as Ikpu-Uzu). They even establish and engage in gold smith industries. In fact, their black smith industries are situated in various localities in Igbo land. The families that own and engage in those black smith industries are called “UMU-UZU”. UMU-UZU are found almost in every nuke and cranny in Igbo land. They work with metals, engaging in various forms of innovative and productive activities like manufacturing, fabrication, and agro-allied products. Igbos are very dogged and influential in business. They are naturally endowed and imbued with entrepreneurial characteristics beyond measure and beyond limit and they exhibit it instinctively any where they are.

In addition to that, Igbo people of eastern Nigeria are naturally blessed with rich arable and fertile land for agriculture. They are richly and naturally blessed with multiple and multidimensional , ever increasing talented men and women. The major food crops obtainable in Eastern Nigeria include but not limited to yam, cassava, rice, cocoyam. Their major cash crops include palm oil, bananas, and several kinds of fruits. Rich reserves and solid minerals and natural resources are **quantomly** available in the south east Nigeria. Such mineral resources include crude oil, natural gas, coal, limestone, marble, granite, salt, lead, zinc. Available agricultural resources include but not limited to cassava, yam, maize, rice, palm oil, rubber, cocoa and assorted types of fruits. Available forest resources include but not limited to Timber, Fuelwood and, Charcoal. Water resources available among others include but not limited to Rivers, Streams and Lakes. Other resources include Sandy soil, Clay soil and Gravel. All these resources are abundant in eastern Nigeria the home of the Ndi Igbo. The following industries have a lot of potential to see investments in Southeast:

- (i) Agro-allied industries: fruit and vegetable canning, cassava flour, and starch
- (ii) Textiles: fishing nets, mosquito nets, and cotton wool.
- (iii) Industrial minerals and quarrying (stone crusher plants, glass industry, tableware, and aggregate factories)
- (iv) The chemical industry that produce bottles, flasks, cans, tubes, bags and tiles are the plastics industry.
- (v) polyethylene products, explosive, self-adhesive tape, pulp, and paper.

The Eastern Nigeria is the home for Igbo people and predominantly dominated by Ndi Igbo. Igbo land is richly blessed with large number of people with entrepreneurial characteristics. Igbo people’s business activities and their approach to entrepreneurship development have been linked to the region’s economic progress. Through entrepreneurial apprenticeship method, many Igbo people have become big time business moguls, captains of industries, accredited manufacturers and service agents and self-reliant, and are living testimony of improved standard of living. The practice of entrepreneurial apprenticeship has led to improved per capita income which is an important indicator of decline in poverty and good measure of economic development and growth (Ajaero, 2015). Entrepreneurial

apprenticeship in Igbo land is an educational method that encompasses the broader process of teaching and learning. It is practical/functional oriented education. It includes formal and informal education aimed at developing cognitive, emotional, social and entrepreneurial competences and management skills. Entrepreneurial apprenticeship can be approached possibly in three different effective and applicable ways namely (a) Imu-ahia (b) Imu-oruaka (c) igba oso afia. It is important to note that Imu-ahia, Imu- oruaka and Igba osoafia are verbs in Igbo language.

These three Igbo words are concepts used to describe three different approaches to entrepreneurial apprenticeship. Hence, the three approaches to entrepreneurial apprenticeship is generally and commonly known in Igbo land as Igba-boyi or Igba odibo, meaning apprenticeship. The practice of entrepreneurial apprenticeship involves sending adolescent children between 11 and 18 years to train and acquire skills in craft, commercial activities or agency. One of the ways to engage in entrepreneurial apprenticeship is Imu-ahia (Commercial apprenticeship). Commercial apprenticeship involves giving the apprentice on the job training, coaching and mentorship in a business. It is carried out under commercial setting, focusing attention on developing skills, knowledge, and expertise in areas like sales, marketing, customer relationship, finance, agency and management.

It includes Serving and learning the nitty-gritties and rudiments of commerce and industry under a commercial or business guru. Another approach to entrepreneurial apprenticeship is Imu-Oruaka (Craft man apprenticeship) which involves the process of on the job training, coaching and mentorship under an experienced craft man to acquire and develop skills, knowledge and experience in a specific trade or craft. The third approach to entrepreneurial apprenticeship is Igba-oso-afia (Agent apprenticeship). Agent apprenticeship involves on the job training, coaching and mentorship under an experienced agent, focusing on developing skills, knowledge and expertise in areas like canvassing, project planning, project analysis, budgeting, project implementation, project execution, sales, marketing, negotiation and customer service, financial intelligence, business management, customer relationship and management, new market development and cash cow management and techniques for reviving sick business.

According to Iwueke, et al. (2020), Igbo entrepreneurial apprenticeships are type of human resource/capital development program that combine training, coaching and mentoring. The Igbo people approach entrepreneurial apprenticeship as a school where the apprentice (students) learns from his master the science and art of establishing, nurturing, managing and growing a small venture to become a business empire. During the apprenticeship period, the Oga (master) in practical terms, assumes the responsibility of teaching, guiding, directing, counseling, coaching and mentoring the apprentice until the boyi (the mentee/student /apprentice) develops competence in the act of doing business.

The training includes practical exposures to nitty-gritties of legitimate hustling and scouting for business opportunities, doing business or market research, business planning, financial intelligence and wisdom), self discipline, resource management (economic wisdom), book keeping and accounting (financial and business recordings and documentation), business and investment analysis, portfolio management, new market entry strategies, business forecasting and market analysis. Risk identification, risk analysis, risk calculation and risk avoidance, proactive behavior, supply chain management, transport and logistics, value creation, opportunity seeking and secretes for business sustainability, resilience, customer centric and business development strategies and growth.

The International Labour Organization (2017) defines apprenticeship as a systematic long-term training for a recognized occupation taking place primarily within an undertaking or under an independent craftsman, governed by a written contract of apprenticeship, and subject to established standards. It is competence development program geared towards enhancing the inborn or innate entrepreneurial capacities of the candidates involved. Two key people are often involved in entrepreneurial apprenticeship, namely the oga (master / mentor) and Nwa boyi (apprentice /mentee).

The Igbo pattern of practicing apprenticeship plays a significant role in the personal economic development and growth and by extension the economic development and growth of Eastern Nigeria. The Igbo apprenticeship style is a form of master-servant joint commitment to economic activity for mutual benefits subsisting for a predetermined period of time. Apprenticeship period allows for an ample time for oga's business to generate enough profit out of which oga will draw from to settle the nwa-boyi to venture on his own. For the oga to settle his boyi very well, the boyi must have been consistently faithful in the service of oga (Agazie, 2012). Both the "Oga" and Nwa-boyi gain from the result of entrepreneurial apprenticeship in a variety of ways. The practice of entrepreneurial apprenticeship accounts for the emergence of Igbo millionaires and billionaires and international business moguls of the Igbo stock (Alake, 2018)

The Igbo people's method of entrepreneurial apprenticeships is the fastest-growing economic engine in the Eastern Nigeria. The Igbo' method of entrepreneurial apprenticeship is an essential component of Igbo economic activities and have evolved into a tradition and culture over the years through which Igbo parents raise their grown offspring to achieve financial success. Both wealthy and poor, educated and uneducated, participates in the entrepreneurial apprenticeship system in Igbo land because it offered them the chance to achieve rapid personal economic and financial success. Through the entrepreneurial apprenticeship programme, Igbo people have become self reliant and self-sufficient under God and this account for up to 80% of Nigeria' GDP, despite getting nothing from government (Amaechi and Netshandama, 2019).

The practice of entrepreneurial apprenticeship in Igbo land is not of recent development. It is as old as Igbo people themselves. The practice of entrepreneurial apprenticeship is deeply rooted in tradition and culture of Igbo people. Though some scholars assert that Igbo apprenticeship practice began after the abolition of slave trade (Isichei, 1976). But deeper investigation revealed that truly, Igbo people did not learn their pattern and practice of entrepreneurial apprenticeship from slave merchants as insinuated in some quarters.

According to (Isichei, 1976), after the slave trade was outlawed in the 19th century, Igbo slaves who had been introduced to entrepreneurship by their masters began engaging in export-oriented ventures.

However, the pattern of entrepreneurial apprenticeship among the Igbo people consists of Imu-Ahia, Imu-Oruaka, and Igba-Oso-Afia. Imu-ahia is commercial apprenticeship, Imu-Oruaka is Craft-man apprenticeship, and Igba oso-afia is agent or broker apprenticeship. Although the three methods of entrepreneurial apprenticeships differ in some respects, they are all focused on entrepreneurial competence development and enhancing the future personal economic development and growth of the individual concerned as noted by (Olulu and Udeora, 2018).

The oga (master / mentor) and nwaboyi (apprentice/ mentee) are involved in the Igbo apprenticeship. A prior establishment of terms and conditions in the form of an agreement are properly made and presented at the beginning of the apprenticeship (Udu, 2015). For

example, a written or verbal agreement is typically entered into between the prospective trainee and master and witnessed by members of both families. Based on the type of entrepreneurship to be engaged in, an agreement is created. When it comes to Imu-Oruaka (craft-man apprentice), the tutor agrees to teach, coach and mentor the apprentice for the entire predetermined duration. Additionally, the potential apprentice must affirm and show that he is prepared to work hard be honesty, and loyalty to his (oga) Master until the predetermined period of time has passed.

As for Imu-Oruaka, the potential apprentice may sometimes be required to pay certain amount of money for Imu-Oruaka (learning of craft/ trade), which would cover his meals, lodging, and other miscellaneous cost. The practice of entrepreneurial apprenticeship among Ndi Igbo have contributed immensely in personal economic development of Igbo people, making the apprentice secure start-up capital through commission or settlement by their masters at the end of his tenure as apprentice (Onyeizugbe, 2020). In the case of Imu-Ahia (commercial apprenticeship), the prospective apprentice and potential Master will determine the number of years the apprentice (Nwa-Odibo) will stay with his Master before he will settle him and let him go freely to establish and manage his own business, according to (Divoke 2014).

1.2 Conceptual Framework

Source: researchers Desk, 2024.

1.3 Aim and Objectives of the study

The study aimed at examining the effect of Entrepreneurial Apprenticeship on personal economic development in Eastern Region of Nigeria. The study was guided by the following specific objectives:

- (1) To determine the correlation between Imu-ahia (commercial apprenticeship) and personal economic development among Igbo people.
- (2) To ascertain the correlation between Imu-Oruaka (craft-man apprenticeship) and personal economic development among Igbo People.
- (3) To determine the relationship between Igba-Oso-afia (Agent/Broker apprenticeship) and personal economic development among Igbo people.

1.4. Research Questions

Based on the above specific objectives, the following research questions are drawn:

- (1) What is the correlation between Imu-ahia (commercial apprenticeship) and personal economic development among Igbo people?
- (2) What is the relationship between Imu-Oruaka (craft-man apprenticeship) and personal economic development among Igbo people?
- (3) What is the relationship between Igba-Osoafia (Broker apprenticeship) and personal economic development among Igbo people?

1.5. Research Hypotheses

Based on the above research questions the following null hypotheses are drawn

H₀₁: there is no significant relationship between Imu ahia (commerce apprenticeship) and personal economic development among Igbo People.

H₀₂: there is no significant relationship between Imu- oruaka (craft-man apprenticeship) and personal economic development among Igbo People.

H₀₃: there is no significant relationship between Igba Oso-afia (Broker apprenticeship) and personal economic development among Igbo people.

2.0 Review of Related Literature

2.1 Conceptual framework

The concept of apprenticeship

According to the International Labour Organization (ILO, 2017), apprenticeship is defined as systematic long-term training for a recognized occupation that takes place primarily within an undertaking or under an independent craftsman, governed by a written contract of apprenticeship as “a job that includes training,” which is too broad as it encompasses all forms of training, both on and off the job. Gonnon (2011) believe what apprenticeship is a mode of leaning that focuses on acquiring specialized skills in order to prepare young adults for society and the workforce. In general apprenticeship offers the apprentice a unique opportunity to get a foot in the door of learning, experience and success.

From the beginning of human history, gurus have passed on their knowledge and abilities to apprentices through a system of practical on-the-job training, coaching and mentorship that offers a platform for developing skills in the unofficial economy. Apprenticeships enable the

unemployed to obtaining and work as journeymen who earn a living wage while gaining experience (Adeyeye, Falola, Waribo, Akinbode, 2015).

Apprenticeship is an effective workforce strategy for connecting people to a variety of professional pathways. This type of work-based learning, sometimes known as a “learn and earn” approach, combines pertinent classroom instruction with on-the-job training. Gradually, the apprentice picks up new abilities and uses them in the workplace while being supervised by a mentor. After completing the program, the apprentice is awarded a credential recognized by the industry.

The person who is being trained, or works for a particular skilled person for a set amount of time in order to master that skill or job is referred to as apprentice (ILO, 2016). Accordingly, an apprentice is typically an adolescent or young person either chooses, or is forced into, engaging in, the and gaining practical and occasionally theoretical, knowledge in a specialized field of interest, or career that they would like to pursue in the future, or make living from.

Because the apprenticeship style of education is adaptable, each program is unique. The needs of the business and professional determine how long an apprenticeship lasts.

2.1. Igbo Apprenticeship

Ndi Igbo people’s culture and traditions are deeply ingrained with the Igbo entrepreneurial apprenticeship style. Initially, there have been conflicting interpretations associated with Ndi Igbo’s propensity for business (Obunike, 2016), venture capital (Chinweuba & Ezeugwu, 2017), and company incubation (Neuwirth, 2017). Igbo entrepreneurship was seen by Agbionu, Emejulu and Egolum (2015) as a mentoring system in which the apprentice is the mentee and the master is the mentor. An additional variation is the apprenticeship, or master-servant relationship (Obunike, 2016). According to Neuwirth, (2017) in both systems, people receive instruction or mentoring from accomplished experts and professionals in a particular field. The Igbo Apprenticeship System was further conceptualised by Ekekwe (2021) as a communal Enterprising Framework, in which successful businesses train others and eventually provide capital and possibly their customers to the new businesses. He claimed that the model’s distinctive feature is that few businesses grow to become extremely dominant because they equal community where everyone has opportunities, no matter how small. This implied that the goal of the Igbo apprenticeship style is to create more just, equitable, and inclusive economic and network systems that benefits everyone, not just a selected few. The apprenticeship system in Igbo country is known by a variety of names, such as Okpu-Uzuna Nwauzu interpreted as black smith and servant, which denotes craftsmanship, and Ogana Nwa-boyi (master and servant), which denotes apprenticeship. Based on the trade or kind of business, these names related to the master-apprentice relationship. There is a suggestion that the Igbo Apprenticeship style is designed to create more just, equitable, and inclusive economic systems that benefit everyone. Not just a selected few. Depending on the trade or kind of business, these titles allude to the relationship between a master and apprentice.

2.1.2 Type of Igbo Entrepreneurship in Brief

There are three types of Igbo entrepreneurship namely: Imu-Ahia, imu-Oruaka and Igba osoafia.

Imu-ahia, Imu-oruaka and Igba-osoafia have been passed from generations. They have evolved into a cultural legacy in the Eastern part of Nigeria. The Igbo people needed to

reclaim their future, which had been stolen from them, hence, the continuity of Imu-ahia. The Igbo cultural practice of entrepreneurial apprenticeship of Imu-ahia, Imu-oruaka and Igba-osoafia was developed and established originally to achieve a number of good and purposeful intentions which among others include eliminating poverty from the society by helping the poor out of poverty, give them sense of belonging and means of livelihood by giving them opportunity to serve and be settled with finance to establish a going concern for themselves, eliminate joblessness, gangsterism and criminality by engaging everyone in a legitimate, meaningful and productive activities. It is deemed that everyone from Igbo Stock needs to be meaningfully and productively engaged. Everyone is expected to find legitimate means of making money and live meaningful life and contribute back to the society by training, coaching and mentoring the younger generation(poor and indigent individual members of the society) and settle them to start life by opening a business for them or giving them money to start business of their own choice after serving apprenticeship.

Imu- ahia otherwise known in literature as Business Coaching is this practice which allows the learners to acquire business knowledge through direct supervision by a master or coach in market or commercial arena. Sometimes, imu ahia is designed to help people who, though knowledgeable in business but lack fund to actualise their dream of owning a business. The major advantage of Imu-Ahia is that it gives, the learner the opportunity to be settled with finance to start his own business and to establish business contacts like producers, suppliers and others considered as aid to successful business.

The next Igbo entrepreneur practice is Imu-Oruaka: this practice is also called hand to tools skill. It entails gaining an in-depth knowledge of a certain profession. The major benefit of this practice is that it allows them learn one more skill.

Igba- osoafia is another form of apprenticeship: this form of apprenticeship involves, training the learner called Odibo (servant) acquiring skill in brokerage. The practice entails sending the learner to live with his/her master while undergoing the training. It usually lasts for a fixed time period of time, ranging from 1-5 years.

2.1.3 Constraint to the Practice of apprenticeship.

Generally, apprenticeship practice in Igbo land faces some challenges that tend to threaten the practice. First is lack of fidelity on the part of the master, in some cases the master finds it difficult to keep or honour the initial agreement between them and the Nwa-Boyi at the completion of the learning or apprenticeship based on insubstantial excuses or reasons.

The second challenge is the case of demise of the Nwa-boi in the cause of serving the apprenticeship. Most times the family of the apprentice is never compensated. The latter case threatened the Igbo apprenticeship (Agomoh, 2010). The practice is further challenged by theft on the part of Nwa-boyi that steals and defrauds the master.

The development impact of the program, thought felt at the individual level. The practice has brought real personal economic development and growth to the Igbo people as individuals by extension to the Igbo land in terms of infrastructural development. Igbos and their entrepreneurial apprenticeship practice are catalyst of development anywhere Igbo man is as most time both Oga (Master) and servant (Nwa boyi) end up developing cities and state where they live to the detriment of their own locality.

2.2. Entrepreneurship

The term entrepreneurship and its related concepts and theories were first used by French writer Richard Cantillon in 1775. Cantillon defined entrepreneurship as any form of self-

employment. Entrepreneurs are risk-takers in an economy where they hope to make money in the long run. Venkataraman (2019) defines entrepreneurship as the discovery and exploitation of profitable opportunities for private wealth and as a consequence for social wealth as well. Davidsson (2006) concluded that entrepreneurship is creation of new economic activity.

To improve the quality of entrepreneurship, there is need to make entrepreneurship education an integral part of education, this is so because, entrepreneurial learning as the active and cognitive processes individual employ as they acquire, retain, and use entrepreneurial competencies. European Commission (2011) defined entrepreneurship education as a process by which learners are equipped with a wide set of competencies that can bring about greater individual, social and economic benefits since the ability gained can be applied in myriad aspects of people' lives. The definition as preferred above implies that through entrepreneurship individual can easily convert creativity, innovation and risk taking acquire the ability to plan and manage projects in order to achieve objectives.

Finally, an entrepreneur is a business-minded person who always finds ways to improve and grow in business. An entrepreneur is a professional who discovers a business opportunity to produce improved or new goods and services and identifies a way in which resources required can be mobilised.

The Igbo apprenticeship entrepreneurship system held the learner to scan the environment, master the act of money making, emerging successful in their chosen endeavour through the exhibition of prudence, consistency, shrewdness, perseverance or doggedness business.

2.2.2 Personal Economic Development in Eastern Nigeria.

Economic development refers, to the process of increasing volume of production, improving technology, raising living standards, altering institution and completely transforming the infrastructure of the country (society for international development, 2021. Put succinctly, it refers to the advancement of the economy's socioeconomic structure. Todaro (2002) viewed economic development as the process of improving the quality of human lives and capabilities by raising people's levels of living, self-esteem, and freedom (Tadaro, 2012). The term national or personal economic development is a process rather than an outcome, it is dynamic in that it involves progressive change from one state or condition to another. Ideally, such change is a positive one.

But economic development and growth of the state is quite different from personal economic development and growth of individuals. Personal economic development of the individuals refers to the process of improving one's economic well being and personal financial stability through education, skill, competence building, strategic decision making, enabling individuals to increase personal income, enhance financial literacy, build personal wealth, achieve personal economic independence, improve quality of life. Personal economic development further includes personal income growth through multiple streams of income, expense management, personal savings and profitable investment, personal debt management and personal financial goal setting and vigorous pursuit.

The benefits of personal economic development includes but not limited to personal economic stability, increased personal financial security, improved standard of living, enhanced personal financial freedom, and better economic and financial decision making skills. Personal economic development is in most cases is influenced by education, skills and training, networking, mentorship, and access to resources. Strategies for personal economic development include but may not be limited to making specific, measurable, achievable, relevant and time bound plans, setting personal financial goals, creating personal budget,

reduction in frivolous, unplanned or unbudgeted spending, invest in education, training and personal self development, develop and establish multiple personal income streams and building an emergency fund through consolidated savings. Personal economic development can be achieved through increasing means of income means, reduced or zero debt, increased savings and enhanced financial literacy.

2.2.3 The Relationship between Entrepreneurship Apprenticeship and personal economic development.

The U.S. Small Business Administration (1998) asserted that the crucial barometer of economic freedom and well-being is the continued creation of new and small firms in all sectors of the economy by all segments of society. The OECD (2008) stated that entrepreneurship is central to the functioning of market economies. Baum et al., (2007) emphasized the importance of entrepreneurship as the economic mechanism that allows for the identification and mitigation of economic inefficiencies.

The essence of entrepreneurship is people, each with unique characteristics and behaviours (roles). In the business sector, an entrepreneur can play a variety of roles. Two key responsibilities of an entrepreneur can be identified in order to illustrate the relationship between entrepreneurship and economic growth and development. The entrepreneur contributes innovation to economic life of the Southeast people. As innovator, the entrepreneur transforms inventions and ideas into economically viable entities, whether or not they create a firm in the process, because of this, some of the most important variables relating entrepreneurship to economic development is newness through start-ups and inventions.

Traditional economic theories treated any disruption, such as entrepreneurial new firms creating whole new industries, as “God sent” external forces and tended to suggest that entrepreneurship hinders rather than encourage growth. Schumpeter established the link between entrepreneurship, innovation, and growth. Classical economics focused on optimising existing resources within a stable environment. More recently, the relationship between entrepreneurship and economic growth has been established by theories of “industrial evolution”. These ideas highlight the importance of knowledge in navigating change and place it at the center. According to the current evolutionary theories, which are backed by actual data, entrepreneurship promote growth for three reasons (Burns, 2011):

1. It increases the number of businesses, which fosters competition. Although this boosts growth on its own, it is a cumulative phenomenon since competition foster knowledge externalities, new ideas, better than local monopolies. Therefore, entrepreneurship promote economic development.
- ii. Entrepreneur facilitates’ knowledge spill over’- the transfer of knowledge from its point of origin to other people or businesses. Knowledge spillover is a key mechanism underlying endogenous growth and start up.

3.0 Research Method

The study adopted correlational research design. The population of study is made up of 150 dealers in food stuffs (respondents) in Ochanja Foodstuff Market in Onicha Anambra state. The basis of selection are: (i) They are into food stuff and provision (ii) have at least eight shops spread across the market (iii) practices Igbo three types entrepreneurship as discussed in the literature(and presently have at least 15 Nwa-boi.), also maintain labour force of at least ten monthly paid workers.

The study adopted the convenience sampling method as only a section of the market was studied. Implying that the population size equals the sample size. The study relied on the use of primary data collected through structured questionnaire; while Spearman rank Order correlation was adopted for testing the Hypotheses.

4.0 Analyses of Data

One Hundred and fifty (150) Questionnaire were distributed to the respondents. A total of one hundred and twenty-seven (127) or 85% of the Questionnaire were successfully retrieved, while twenty-three Questionnaire were either not retrieved or were rejected because of inappropriate filling.

Table 4.1 Response Rate and Descriptive Statistics for Economic development

S/N	Item	SA	A	MA	DA	SDA	N	Mean	STD
1	Technological change is an indicator economic development	57	50	1	10	9	127	4.071	0.710
2	Innovation across different sector is a reflection of the level of development	55	50	1	9	12	127	4.000	0.5621
3	Improved welfare is a strong indicator of economic development	56	48	2	11	10	127	4.015	0.768
4	Economic growth is an integral part of economic development	51	50	5	9	12	127	3.9	0.865
5	Real economic development is a reflection of disruptive technology	50	48	3	16	10	127	3.882	0.7432

In table 4.1 above, question 1 seeks to verify if technological change is a good measure of economic development. The result shows that 57 respondents strongly agree, 50 agree, 1 respondent moderately agree. 10 disagreed while 9 strongly disagree. The mean score of 4.071 indicate a strong agree by the respondent that technological change is a good measure of economic development. Question two attempts to ascertain if innovation across board effective measure economic development. 55 respondents strongly agree, 50 just agree, 1 person moderately agree, 9 disagree, and finally 12 respondents strongly disagree. Again, a mean score of 4.000 indicate a strong agreement that innovation across different sector is a reflection of economic development. Question three seeks to ascertain if improved welfare is a strong indicator of economic development. The result shows that 56 respondents strongly agree, 48 simply agree, 2 moderately agree, while 11 respondents disagree. Lastly, 10 respondents strongly disagree. The mean score of 4.015 is a strong indicator that majority of the respondents agree to the question that Improved welfare is a strong indicator of economic development.

The fourth question seeks to ascertain if economic growth is an integral part of economic development. The result obtained showed that 51 respondents strongly agree, 50 simply agree, while 5 moderately agree. 9 respondents disagree with the statement, while 12 respondents strongly disagree. The mean value of 3.937 shows a strong agreement to the question that economic growth is an integral part of economic development. Finally, question five seeks to ascertain if real economic development is a reflection of disruptive technology. The result shows that 50 respondents strongly agree, 48 agree, 3 moderately agree, Furthermore, 16 respondents disagree while 10 strongly disagree. The mean score of 3.882 support the opinion that real economic development is a reflection of disruptive technology.

Table 4.2 Response Rate and Descriptive Statistics for Entrepreneurial Apprenticeship

S/N	Imu –ahia (Commercial Apprenticeship)	SA	A	MA	DA	SDA	N	Mean	STD
1	Commerce entrepreneurship is the best form of apprenticeship to learn	45	42	3	19	18	127	3.606	0.7103
2	Those who learn this type of skill are more successful in life than other two	48	40	11	10	18	127	3.707	0.7103
3	It has more advantage than disadvantage	40	42	10	15	20	127	3.528	0.924
Imu-Oruaka (Craft man apprenticeship)		SA	A	MA	DA	SDA	N	Mean	STD
1	this type of apprenticeship makes the learner less dependent on the Master settling him/her	58	52	0	7	9	127	4.102	0.7103
2	I will strongly suggest this form of apprenticeship to future skill hunters.	55	50	1	9	12	127	4.000	0.5621
3	It worth emphasizing than others.	40	42	10	15	20	127	3.528	0.924
Igba-Oso afia (Broker Apprenticeship)		SA	A	MA	DA	SDA	N	Mean	STD
1	This type of apprenticeship will help the learner to easily access mentor	57	53	2	5	9	127	4.102	0.7103
2	It is the best form of raising business fund	58	52	0	7	9	127	4.102	0.7103
3	There is high risk of disappointment on both sides.	45	42	3	19	18	127	3.606	0.7231

Table 4.2 shows the data analysis on entrepreneurial apprenticeship. The table is divided into three sections. Section one questions dwell on commerce (Imu-Ahia) form of apprenticeship. The first question in section one seeks to ascertain if Imu-Ahia form of entrepreneurship is relatively more preferable to the other two (Imu-Oruaka and Igba-osoafia by asking: Commerce entrepreneurship is the best form of apprenticeship to learn, the response shows that 45 respondent strongly agree, 42 simply agree, 3 moderately agree, while 19 and 18 disagree and strongly disagree respectively. The mean score of 3.606 implies that on average majority of the respondents agree the view that Commerce entrepreneurship is the best form of apprenticeship to learn. The second question seeks to ascertain the respondents view on the relative advantage of each form of apprenticeship by asking, those who learn commerce are more successful in life than other two form of entrepreneurship. 48 strongly agree, 40 simply agree, 11 moderately agree; while 10 disagree finally, 18 respondents strongly disagree. The mean score of 3.709 and a standard deviation value of 0.7021 are strong affirmation that those who learn this type of skill are more successful in life than other two form of apprenticeship. The third question framed as “It has more advantage than disadvantage” aimed at ascertaining if there are relative advantage in learning any of the apprenticeship. The response affirmed that 40 strongly agree, 42 simply agree, 10 moderately agree, 15 disagreed while 20 strongly disagree. The mean score of 3.528 affirmed that on the average most respondents agree that commerce apprenticeship has more advantage than disadvantage.

The questions on skill acquisition (Imu-Oruaka) are analysed as follows: The first question on this type of apprenticeship makes the learner less dependent on the Master settling him/her aimed at ascertaining which of the apprenticeship has more benefit than the other in terms of dependence on the master. Response to Question one, are as follows 58 respondents strongly agree, 52 simply agree, 0 moderately agree while 7 and 9 disagree and strongly disagree respectively. The mean score of 4.102 is a very strong affirmation that skill acquisition makes the learner less dependent on their master. Question two was framed to elicit information on the extent of importance the respondents attached to the three forms of apprenticeship. 55 respondents strongly agree, 50 simply agree, 1 moderately agree, 9 disagree while 12 strongly

disagree. The mean score of 4.000 strongly support the view that skill acquisition is more preferred to the other form of apprenticeship. Finally, question three aimed at highlighting the relative worthiness of each form of apprenticeship. The response shows that 40 strongly agree that skill acquisition is more important than the other two forms of apprenticeship. 42 simply agree, 10 moderately agree, 15 disagree, while 20 strongly disagree. The mean score of 3.528 suggest that on the average, the respondents prefer skill acquisition to the other two forms of apprenticeship.

The third form of apprenticeship is the servant or Igba-osoafia type. The first question seeks to ascertain the relative ease with which each form of apprenticeship allows the apprenticeship to access mentor. 57 strongly agree, 53 agree, 2 moderately agree, while 5 and 9 disagree and strongly disagree respectively. The mean value of 4.102 strongly support the view that this type of apprenticeship will help the learner to easily access mentor. The second question seek to ascertain if servant – master relationship is the best form of raising investment fund. 58 respondents strongly agree, 52 simply agree, 0 respondents moderately agree, while 7 disagree. Finally, 9 strongly disagree. The mean value of 4.102 is a strong affirmation that majority of the people that Igba-osoafia is a reliable source of raising business capital. The third question was an attempt to ascertain the relative degree of being disappointed after the agreed period of the Igba-osoafia. The response shows that 45 respondents strongly agree, 42 simply agree, 3 moderately agree, while 19 disagree, 18 strongly disagree. The mean score of 3.606 implies that on the average, majority of the respondents agreed that the likelihood of disappointment is high in igba-osoafia.

Table 4.4 Distribution for apprenticeship Entrepreneurship and economic development

Parameter	N	Minimum	Maximum	Mean	STD
Economic development	127	1	5	3.974	0.72862
Imu-Ahia	127	1	5	3.614	0.7815
Imu-Oruaka	127	1	5	3.877	0.7321
Igba-Osoafia	127	1	5	3.914	0.7139

Table 4.4 is the summary of the descriptive statistics used to analyse the responses to the questions provided by the participants in the study.

Table 4.5 Interpretation of the various mean and standard deviation(STD) values recorded in the study

S/N	Mean value	Remark	STD. value	Remark
1	$X < 3.39$	Low association	$SD < .5$	Low spread of opinion
2	3.40 to 3.59	Moderate Association	$SD > .5$	Acceptance to majority view
3	3.60 and above	High association	$SD > 1$	High disagreement

Source: Marson (2014)

4.2 Secondary analysis (Test of Hypotheses)

Spearman rank Order correlation coefficient will be applied to analyse the data or ascertain the extent of relationship between apprenticeship entrepreneurship and economic development in Southeast. All test to be conducted at 95% degree of confidence. Implying level of significance is fixed at 0.05 or 5% where $PV < 0.05$ imply significant association between study variables (apprenticeship entrepreneurship and economic development) and falsification of the null hypotheses. If $PV > 0.05$ would imply insignificant level of associations between the variables and acceptance of the null hypothesis.

The Spearman Rank Order Correlation Coefficient was adopted as the correlation tool as a result of its non-parametric features (Normality of distribution, homogeneity of variables) and its suitability for the data which is either scaled on interval or ordinal level of scaling. In order to achieve the objectives designed for this study, the formulated research hypotheses were tested based on the review literature concerning apprenticeship entrepreneurship.

H₀₁: There is no significant relationship between commercial apprenticeship style of entrepreneurship and economic development in the Southeast region of Nigeria.

4.6 Correlation between economic development and Apprenticeship entrepreneurship

			Imu-Ahia	Economic development
Spearman's Rho	Imu-Ahia	Correlation coefficient	1.000	.788**
		Sig(2-tailed)	.	.000
		N	127	127
Economic development		Correlation coefficient	.788**	1.000
		Sig (2-tailed)	.000	.
		N	127	127

****Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed)**

The result of the tested hypothesis with rho value of 0.788 indicates a positive relationship between both variable (dependent variable- apprenticeship entrepreneurship and the independent variable- economic development). R-square is the coefficient of determination of the correlation is 0.621 ($0.788^2=0.621$) or 62.1% of the variation in the dependent variable, Onicha main Market was explained by the independent variable Imu-Ahia apprenticeship style of Igbo entrepreneurship. The above result shows that p-value (0.001) is less than 0.0001 level of significant. Based on the above result the null hypothesis is rejected, the alternative hypothesis is accepted. Therefore, we conclude that Imu-Ahia form of Apprenticeship style in entrepreneurial activity plays vital role in economic development of Igbo people in Southeast region of Nigeria.

H₀₂: There is no significant relationship between skill acquisition (Imu-Oruka) apprenticeship style of entrepreneurship and economic development

4.7 Correlation between economic development and Apprenticeship entrepreneurship

			Imu-Oruaka	Economic Development
Spearman's Rho	Imu-Oruaka	Correlation coefficient	1.000	.856**
		Sig (2-tailed)	.	.000
		N	127	127
Economic Development		Correlation Coefficient	.856**	1.000
		Sig (2-tailed)	.000	.
		N	127	127

****Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level(2-tailed)**

The relationship between Imu-Oruaka and Economic development is revealed to be significant given the observed correlation 0.856 and p-value of 0.00 which is less than 0.05 (Table 4.7 above). The correlation value shows a strong and significant relationship between both variables at 95% confidence interval. The positive sign value of $r=0.856$ reveal a direct

relationship between Imu-Oruaka and economic development. The result indicates that the more Imu-Oruaka apprenticeship acquired in Igbo land the more economically they will develop. Therefore, the hypothesis of no significant relationship between Imu-Oruak and Economic development in Southeast (Null) hypothesis is rejected on the decision rule of $P < 0.05$. We therefore accept the alternative, and restate the null hypothesis that there is significant relationship between Imu-Oruaka and economic development in the Southeast Nigeria.

H0₃: There is no significant relationship between serving as servant (Igba-osoafia) apprenticeship entrepreneurship and economic development in Southeast.

4.8 Correlation between economic development and Apprentice Entrepreneurship

		Igba-Osoafia	Economic Development
Spearman's Rho	Igba-osoafia	1.000	.899**
	Correlation coefficient		
	Sig (2-tailed)	.	0.000
	N	127	127
Economic development	Economic development	.899**	1.000
	Correlation coefficient		
	Sig (2-tailed)	.000	.
	N	127	127

***Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed)*

The relationship between Igba-Osoafia and economic development is revealed to be significant given the observed correlation value of .899 and a P-value of 0.000 which is less than 0.05 (Table 4.8 above). The correlational value shows a strong and significant relationship between both variable at a 95% confidence interval. The positive sign value of $r = 0.899$ reveals a direct relationship between Igba-Osoafia and economic development. The significant value is less than 0.05, which means that the variation explained by the model is not due to chance. This indicates that the more, Igba-Osoafia youths serve the more developed the economy of Southeast. Therefore, the hypothesis of no significant relationship between Igba-osoafia and economic development in Southeast (Null) hypothesis is rejected based on the decision rule of $P < 0.05$. We therefore accept the alternative hypothesis and restate the null that Igba-Osoafia is significantly related to economic development of Southeast region of Nigeria.

4.9 Discussion of Finding

The relationship between apprenticeship entrepreneurship and economic development in the Southeast is revealed to be positive. Meaning that to achieve economic development in south east government need to encourage the three types of Apprenticeship as discussed and tested in this study. This outcome is empirical validation of the theoretical conclusion in Apprenticeship manual (2013). The result obtained in this study affirmed the theoretical believe that serving as servant (Igba-osoafia) is a reliable source of start up capital for SMEs, this empirical finding support the earlier work of Adeola and Ozigbo (2021), that the more Igbos practice Igba-osoafia the richer they becomes and the more they will emerge as business owners.

Findings.

The study explored into the Igbo peoples' kind of entrepreneurship under the entrepreneurial apprenticeship. The practice is as old as the Igbo society. The present study identified three types of entrepreneurial apprenticeship namely: Imu-ahia, Imu-Oruaka and Igba-osoafia. That the common or single word used in describing imu-ahia, imu oruaka and igba osoafia is igba boyi. Each of this form of entrepreneurial apprenticeship play different and significant role in empowering the members of the society and they achieve a common result in terms of personal economic prosperity, development, growth and economic sustainability of Igbo people. Ceteris paribus, That Igbo type of entrepreneurial apprenticeship involves the process of incubating, nurturing and supporting entrepreneurs and startups, providing resources, guidance and expertise to help them grow and succeed, ultimately becoming business moguls. The result of the empirical result affirmed that the most-easiest way to access investment capital is through Igba boyi (Roberts, 2015), while Onyima et al., (2018) concluded that over 60% of all successful business are owned by those that have passed through Igba-boyi through Imu-Afia, reason being that they can easily access cash. The study also affirmed that, Imu-Oruaka help the learner to be self-reliant, access to mentorship whenever the need arises (Nnoyelu and Onyезugbe, 2020)

Findings revealed that Igbo practice of entrepreneurial apprenticeship is one of the best ways of identifying, developing, and empowering multiple entrepreneurs and potential business leaders, creating ripple effect of innovative entrepreneurship, self employment, personal economic growth and job creation. That Igbo practice of entrepreneurial apprenticeship fosters entrepreneurial ecosystem, develops scalable business models, create industry leaders, stimulate economic growth and enhance competitiveness. That oga usually galvanize his settled apprentices into a network of friends and business associates for collaborations, assistance and mutual help. It is revealed that in most cases, if the oga (master) lost his business, that his network of friends and associates, especially his former apprentices may rally around him, contributing money and reinstate him back to business. That is one of the essential benefits of training and settling as many apprentice as possible within the stipulated and agreed time.

Conclusion.

The study concluded that the three forms of entrepreneurial apprenticeship as identified are all important and serve as panaceas for achieving personal economic development and growth by empowering the learner with some good financial assistance and good managerial ability.

5.2 Recommendation

The study recommends as follows

- (i) To ensure speedy personal economic development of Southeast, south east governors should integrate Imu-ahia into academic curriculum of South east students. This will enable them prepare and choose the particular apprenticeship to learn.
- (ii) Government should set aside at least 20% of total revenue accruing to their state to serve as investment fund to enable newly graduated apprentice access loan for business take off, stipend should be paid government to apprentice while they are on training.
- (iii) Igba-boi should not be construed as indirect or domestic slavery. Parties to entrepreneurial apprenticeship practice must have clearly defined agreement to protect the interest of both parties to avoid any of the part failing to keep to agreement.

References

- . Iwueke, O. C.; Halima, S. A. & Oparaku, P. N. (2020). Apprenticeship Training System and Business Sustainability in Anambra State South East Nigeria, *International Journal of Innovative Research in Social Sciences and Strategic Management Techniques*, 7(1): 184-193
- Adeola, O. and Ozigbo, V. C., (2021). *Igbo Boi: Repositioning the Igbo Apprenticeship System*, Lagos: Prima Imprint, Nigeria.
- Ajaero, C. (2015). The Igbo Apprenticeship System. A model for Sustainable Development in Africa. *Journal of Economic Development, Management, IT, Finance and Marketing*, 7(2), 14-24.
- Alake, M. (2018). The Igbo apprenticeship system that builds wealth and started the incubation system.
- Amaechi, K. E. & Netshandama, V. (2019). The igba-boi Apprenticeship Approach: Arsenal Behind Growing Success of Igbo Entrepreneurs in Nigeria, *Ubuntu: Journal of Conflict and Social Transformation*, Special Issue: 227-25
- Apprenticeship Manual (2013). What You Need to Know to Hire an Apprentice, Brazil Ministry of Labour and Employment.
- Baum, J.R., J.D. Olian, M. Erez, E.R. Schnell, K.G. Smith, H.P. Sims, J.S. Scully and K.A. Smith (2017), Nationality and work role interactions: a cultural contrast of Israeli and US entrepreneurs' versus managers' needs, *Journal of Business Venturing* 8, 499-512
- Baumol, W. J., 1990. Entrepreneurship: Productive, Unproductive, and Destructive, *Journal of Political Economy*, 98(5), pp. 893-921.
- Burns, P., 2011. *Entrepreneurship and small business*, Palgrave Macmillan, New York, p. 516
- Davidsson, P. (2006), Culture, structure and regional levels of entrepreneurship, *Entrepreneurship and Regional Development* 7, 41-62
- Diyoke, C. I. (2014). Entrepreneurship development in Nigeria: issues, problems and prospects. *International Journal of Technical Research and Applications*, 10 (1), 19-23
- European Commission (2010). *Convergence Report (2011)*. *European Economy*, 3, 2010
- Gonnon, P. (2011). Apprenticeship as a model for the international architecture of TVET," in *Assuring the Acquisition of Enterprise: Foreign Language and Research Press*, 33 – 42
- ILO (2017). *Toolkit for Quality Apprenticeships, Vol. I: Guide for policy makers*. Geneva, Switzerland: International Labour Organisation
- Iwara, I. O.;
- Neuwirth, R. (2018), "Igbo apprenticeship system is world's largest business incubator platform - Robert Neuwirth reveals", available at: <https://www.informationng.com/2018/11/igbo-apprenticeshipsystem-isworlds-largest-business-incubator-platform-robertneuwirth-reveals.html> (accessed 15 August 2019)
- Nnonyelu, N. & Onyeizugbe, C. (2020). Reimagining Igbo Apprenticeship: Bringing it up to Speed with Contemporary Realities, *European Journal of Business and Management Research*, 5(3): 1-8
- OECD, 2008. *Measuring Entrepreneurship: A Digest of Indicators*", OECD, Paris, www.oecd.org
- Olulu, R. M. & Udeorah, S. (2018). Contract of apprenticeship and employment generation in Nigeria. *International Journal of Scientific Research in Education*, 1(3), 335-344
- Onyima, J. K. C. ; Nzewi, N. & Chiekezie, O. M. (2013). Effects of Apprenticeship and Social Capital on New Business Creation Process of „Immigrant“ Entrepreneurs, *Review of Public Administration and Management*, 2(3): 1-11
- Roberts Neuwirt (2015). The Igbo Apprenticeship System for Wealth Creation, *African Journal of Arts and Humanities*, 5(4); 56-70